

DEFORMATION MECHANISMS OF FIBRE REINFORCEMENTS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FABRICATION OF COMPLEX STRUCTURAL PARTS

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The theoretical modes of deformation for fibre arrays are first identified and then shown to encompass the available forms of reinforcement. In spite of the practical restrictions on these materials, it is shown that each class of material may be extremely deformed, and suitable handling techniques are presented. It emerges that there is no universally preferred form; cloths, continuous and discontinuous prepreg all have mutually complementary features and these are compared. Finally, in a single example it is shown how production routes may be made simpler and more reliable by adopting this formal approach to the craft of shaping and moulding.

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INTRODUCTION

Manufacturers of lightweight composite components are often compelled to make critical decisions between competing classes of reinforcement purely on the basis of mechanical tests on flat laminates, and their craftsmen's experience of shaping properties. If they are fortunate an approximation to the final component shape required can be produced by tape laying or winding, otherwise the choice may be to lay up some type of unidirectional prepreg or cloth. In either case, the formation of a final, detailed shape is greatly assisted by an understanding of the deformations possible in the reinforcement, before it is finally cast in resin.

A first objective must be to avoid large scale discontinuities in the reinforcing layers, and to minimise the amount of handling necessary to produce a given shape, which has adverse effects on time, cost and reproducibility. If the number of mouldings is to be small, ease of handling a reinforcement may assume greater importance than its total capacity for deformation. Where numbers are large, the ability to create a shape instantly from a flat sheet may be more important, and the deformation limits for sheet metal used in the car industry make a useful point of comparison here (Fig. 1). An additional factor, frequently understated, is the need not only to develop a shape with ease, but to place the fibres in correct directions while doing so.

The experimental measurements and analysis described here first illuminate the limits which arise, the type, number and extent of deformations available in existing materials, and then discuss how these influence both the component fabrication route, and the future development of reinforcements.

Leaving aside for a moment the questions of how much deformation is needed, it is necessary to look at the mechanisms of deformation^[1].

A fully triangulated set of continuous fibres (Fig. 2a) should be inextensible in any direction (discounting fibre stretching) whereas a continuous fibre cross ply such as a cloth or a filament wound preform (Fig. 2b) should be deformable in shear, as shown, but be inextensible parallel to the two sets of fibres. Continuous fibre prepreg (Fig. 2c) ought to be deformable transverse to the fibre in tension and compression, and also in shear parallel to the fibre. However, if the fibres are discontinuous (Fig. 2d), deformation parallel and transverse to the fibre should be permitted as well as shear. Because random mats are well triangulated deformation is only possible, if, as for discontinuous, the fibres can still slip past one another.

The presence of an uncured resin or binder in the fibre network tends to pin fibres together where they cross, so that higher loads are required to slip them past one another (a desirable addition to a loose felt) but hardly impairs their ability to rotate, which is essential to fabrics and also makes for stable extension of felts.

Commercially available unidirectional prepregs tend to split between the tows and so are not very extensible in the transverse direction. This tendency can be reduced by using two or more felts bonded together, either with the plies parallel but overlapping, or at a very slight cross ply angle.

Another way of looking at these modes of deformation is to consider how many free edges are required in the shaping process (Fig. 3). This shows that for deformation over a small section of a sphere a cloth requires two free edges, since warp and weft fibres must both change direction. For continuous fibre prepreg (prepared as above) only one free edge is required for the fibres to shear past one another. Discontinuous prepreg needs no free edges to cover a shape of this sort because the fibres can slip over one another.

Looked at in these ways the most deformable material is discontinuous prepreg with three independent deformation modes, and the least deformable is cloth with one deformation mode and requiring two free edges for shaping.

Fig. 1 Forming limit diagram for steel and aluminium.

Fig. 2

Deformation modes of various styles of reinforcement.

This order, with continuous prepreg more freely deformable than cloth is of course at variance with the balance of experience, so the properties required in a practically deformable material must be considered. It is most easy to do this material by material, taking the obvious anomaly first.

DEFORMATION BEHAVIOUR OF CONTINUOUS PREPREG

At first sight it is difficult to visualise continuous prepreg as deformable, this is due to the interaction of three factors.

(1) Transverse stretching

The ability of the prepreg to stretch transversely is obscured by the tendency to split between the plies. Even in smooth, rolled prepreg, boundaries exist between tows which have very few fibres covering them, thus when the material is stretched most of the deformation occurs in these regions. This leads to a large strain concentration effect and tearing between tows at very low overall strain. If as previously suggested two or more prepregs are bonded together with their tows overlapping then transverse deformation becomes possible. Transverse strains of 30% have been introduced into prepared prepregs without evidence of tearing.

(2) Shear

The possibilities for shear are largely obscured by the relative stiffness of this deformation mode (and by the tendency to transverse splitting). If the prepreg is warmed then the ability of the material to deform in this way becomes apparent as the required loads fall off rapidly.

(3) Buckling of the material out of the plane deformation

When attempting to produce uniform shearing this effect becomes apparent. The loads required to produce transverse buckles are lower than those to produce shear and if any transverse stretching present is non-uniform then buckling will occur unless suppressed.

The shape in Fig. 3 was made taking account of all these factors which allowed 17% deformation by shear to produce the distortion shown.

For longer shapes or more complex ones the difficulties multiply. It is increasingly difficult to exert control over longer lengths of sheared material and great care would have to be taken.

These practical constraints whilst certainly relegating continuous prepreg from its second place in the table of deformable materials still leave it with some useful properties. Thus for small mouldings of low complexity it may well be possible to use deformed continuous prepreg as the reinforcement, with the advantage over cloth of controlled orientation.

DEFORMATION BEHAVIOUR OF CLOTHS

For most practical purposes a cloth behaves in deformation as a pin-jointed net of fibres and thus deforms only by angular rotation between warp and weft. (Exceptions are for unprepregged cloth in which the sheet size is not large enough to prevent slippage of tows past one another at constant angular relation). If we assume that the cloth behaves as a pin-jointed net (which has been verified experimentally)^[1] then the relationship between elongation and cross ply angle, as shown in Fig. 4, is

$$\frac{l_1}{l_2} = \frac{\cos \theta_1}{\cos \theta_2}$$

Fig. 3

Effect of deformation over part of a sphere on continuous fibre prepreg and on cloth.

Fig. 4 Deformation parameters for cloth materials.

If cloth or other cross ply is known to behave in this pin-jointed manner then the range of possibilities open may be increased by changing the initial angle between warp and weft from 45° . In the case of cloth this can be done by stretching the cloth first in one direction, then in another. For example, if a piece of cloth is taken with warp and weft at $\pm 45^\circ$ and is then stretched to give $\pm 25^\circ$, we can see from Fig. 5 that this is capable of an extension of about 67% if taken back to $\pm 45^\circ$, or of 114% if taken to $\pm 65^\circ$. This can be represented graphically as:

The practical possibilities of this device are yet to be fully explored but it will, for instance, allow a flanged cylinder to be made by easing out one end of a cylinder at $\pm 25^\circ$ to give a flange which is twice the diameter of the cylinder. The combinations of extension, width reduction and change in area produced in this way are shown in Figs. 5, 6 and 7. The effects of these fibre rotations on cured laminate strength should be calculable at least approximately from the individual ply strengths and the final angle between them, together with changes in the material thickness due to the change in area. The practical values will also depend on the interactions between the two sets of fibres such as increased kinking and possible fibre abrasion at crossover points.

A word must be said about why a material which is so limited in the theoretical sense is so practically useful. Firstly, whilst at least two free edges are undoubtedly necessary for deformation, it is usual to first cut the cloth to size before deformation. This releases all the free edges necessary. Even when the cloth is being deformed on a mould free edges are usually available ahead of the area in which deformation is proceeding.

The second point is perhaps the most important in practical terms. If we take a strip of cloth and stretch it at 45° to a fibre axis the load extension curve is of the form given in Fig. 8. The load rises slowly with extension up to about 25% extension then rises rapidly as the warp and weft begin to interact strongly. This means that for all practical purposes the deformation is reversible and that any shape within the range achievable with cloth can be made by repeated attempts until successful, without damage to the cloth. Thus cloth is the ideal material for an inexperienced fabricator wishing to use deformable materials in hand-layup, as all other materials have non-reversible deformations. If mechanical shaping is used then this advantage no longer holds since once the mould is closed no re-arrangement of the reinforcement is possible. If mechanical forming is to be used then, as for continuous prepreg, restraint must be used on the cloth to prevent buckling, which remains the softest deformation mode. The form of the load-extension curve can act as a disadvantage in that once the warp-weft interaction is high no more accommodation is possible, either to fill the mould or for local detailing.

The last point also arises from the way in which cloth deforms. For a cloth stretched at $\pm 45^\circ$, an extension of about 30% is possible for a width reduction to 55% of the original, and it is this width reduction that plays an important role in shaping cloth. For most deformable materials deformation proceeds by a thinning of the material such that to produce a hemisphere, over 50% extension would be needed. However, with cloth a $\pm 45^\circ$ deformation proceeds by thickening, so that the perimeter of the cloth is shortened and it is this that enables hemispheres to be drawn from cloth.

DEFORMATION BEHAVIOUR OF ALIGNED DISCONTINUOUS PREPREG

This unidirectional prepreg is prepared by dispersing short fibres in glycerine ², so that the fibres can then be aligned by convergent flow through a nozzle and laid down on a filter bed. In the present process the excess glycerine

Fig. 5 Increase in length compared with final ply angle for a cloth under tension.

Fig. 6 Final width compared with final ply angle for a cloth under tension.

Fig. 7 Final area compared with final ply angle for a cloth under tension.

Fig. 8 Load extension curves for aligned discontinuous prepreg and cloth.

is removed by centrifugal action to produce a highly aligned, but damp, felt. This felt is then washed, dried and impregnated with resin to give a sheet of prepreg 1 metre wide x 2 metres long with the fibres aligned in the long direction.

The factors which limit the amount of available deformation are different for this material than for the other materials considered¹. When the prepreg is stretched a load/extension curve of the form shown in Fig. 8 is obtained. Since a falling load curve is by definition unstable the maximum on the load/extension curve is taken as the maximum deformation for unsupported prepreg. Beyond this point local thinning or tearing of the material can occur which will reduce the cured strength. Fig. 9 shows how the maximum load and elongation varies with ply angle for single plies of discontinuous aligned prepreg.

It has also been shown that changes in sample length and crosshead rate affect the extension at maximum load. For an axially aligned strip strained at 50 mm/minute the extension is 4-5% for a 100 mm gauge length, but 11% for a 20 mm gauge length and 18% at a 10 mm gauge length, the maximum load also rises in a similar way. If the extension is applied a little at a time to a 100 mm long strip below the load maximum and time is allowed for relaxation between loadings, then the material can be stretched more without showing signs of damage. For example, a strip with the fibres parallel to the load can be strained 10% rather than 5% without apparent damage or non-uniformity.

Once the prepreg has passed its maximum load point, tears will rapidly develop unless the prepreg can be constrained to deform uniformly. This can be done, for instance, by affixing the prepreg to a rubber backing sheet and stretching both materials together. In this case more than 20% axial deformation has been imposed without signs of non-uniformity. (At this elongation unsupported prepreg would be failing rapidly). Even greater uniform strains have been generated using a cloth as the backing sheet; up to 45%; but this is not always a practical fabrication method.

Combined rotation and slippage of crossplied prepreg

If the plies are first well bonded together by a combination of heat and pressure then deformation proceeds by fibre rotation as for cloth materials eg a $\pm 45^\circ$ cross-ply will elongate 30% with a 50% width reduction. Failure in this case usually proceeds by separation of the plies followed by a tearing of individual plies. If the plies are very well bonded then this available elongation increases to over 40% (the theoretical limit) but with fibre rotation ceasing about $\pm 11^\circ$. Thus both fibre rotation and fibre slippage can occur in this case. The same effects occur with cross ply angles above and below those obtainable with a cloth, eg a 20° cross ply will elongate 12% (ie 5% by fibre rotation, the rest by fibre slippage) and a $\pm 70^\circ$ layup has been stretched 190%, with the load/extension curve having a long plateau rather than a sharp maximum. Whilst such elongation might be unnecessary, the ability to form low angle cross plies which will stretch more than would be expected by fibre rotation should be useful. Cross plies with a very small included angle (such as $\pm 1^\circ$) can provide large transverse extensions purely by fibre rotation and without significant change of fibre orientation. This may be a controlling influence in the transverse stretching of nominally unidirectional prepregs, for example.

Since there is no deformation limit due to fibre interaction, both local accommodation and greater deformation than available with cloth are possible.

Bonded, multiaxial arrays can be made which are still deformable, and indeed this can represent one form of support for the layers which are being deformed in the fibre direction. Such fibre arrays may of course be embossed since this property only depends on the ability to stretch along a fibre axis.

Effect of stretching on cured strength

As previously noted, if the prepreg is stretched unsupported beyond its maximum load, flaws will develop which degrade the cured strength. For example material stretched 6% along its fibre axis loses 30% of its initial UTS¹ whereas 50% trans-

Fig. 9 Maximum load and elongation compared with ply angle for single plies of discontinuous aligned prepreg. Tested without constraint.

Fig. 11 Component made from cloth and discontinuous aligned prepreg via a generic preform.

verse stretch has very little effect. If stretching is carried out on short gauge lengths then of course these effects are much delayed, as they will be for highly constrained supported prepreg. A $0^\circ \pm 60^\circ$ layup in which the $\pm 60^\circ$ plies provide this support has been stretched 19% in the 0° direction. The laminate pressed from this layup was significantly stronger than the unstretched laminate with no increase in variability. This illustrates how effective constraint can be in suppressing damage to the prepreg during deformation.

KNITTING

A review of deformable reinforcements would be incomplete without comment on knitted structures. Knitting is a relative cheap process and for serious production it should be possible to have a generic preform knitted with regard to a given shape to reduce the deformations necessary and simplify construction.

Comparing knitted to other reinforcements, the following points can be made:

It behaves like a woven material in that its deformation is controlled by interactions between the yarns, giving its load/extension curve the same stable form as that for woven cloth.

It is capable of at least 50% elongation in any direction and thus can be made to fit very complex shapes. In principle, very large extensions can be stored in the loops of yarn, as the garment industry has frequently shown.

After moulding, the fibres are arranged roughly randomly in the plane with some fibre looping out of the plane to make the stitches. This will give it relatively poor average properties - probably only a little higher than those of a three-dimensional moulding compound. However, the variability should be much lower since it is certain that there is fibre in every position, which would greatly increase the safe design in practice.

FABRICATION CONSIDERATIONS

It has been shown that these four materials all possess some measure of deformability, the amount of deformation available in single sheets can be superimposed on the metal forming diagram shown earlier for comparison (Fig. 10). It can be seen that the more deformable materials are roughly comparable with metals. The lines shown for aligned discontinuous prepreg represent amounts of deformation that have been achieved without apparent non-uniformity, and are not necessarily maxima. As for the metals any deformations below the lines drawn are safely possible. Figures in the negative minor strain area for prepreg are somewhat arbitrary as they depend on the nature of the support used. The lines for cloth are also comparable with those for metals with the difference that the minor strains must be negative, and any given line represents what will be the minor strain for any major strain.

Table 1 lists the major properties of each material and suggests the sorts of components that would be most suited to that form of reinforcement. It can be seen from this and from the metal-forming diagram that these materials are in essence complementary.

For any particular task one material would usually be the best choice. Cloth represents probably the simplest-to-use material but in general would not be the best from the point of view of stressing. Aligned discontinuous prepreg is capable of the widest application with its unique shaping properties as a single sheet, its cloth-like deformation as a biaxial array, and its ability to take deformation or embossing as a multiaxial layup so as to match loading patterns. On the other hand it is less easy to use than cloth, and for simple unidirectional mouldings inferior in properties to continuous prepreg.

For the optimum use of materials, mixtures of these materials might prove beneficial. For instance the use of aligned discontinuous prepreg with cloth gives a material retaining part of the character of cloth, but also providing the third

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FIG 10

Forming limit diagram for cloth and aligned discontinuous prepreg.

Type	Strain hardening load/extension curve (reversible)	Number of desirable deformation modes	Modes in order of decreasing hardness (Buckling is always the softest mode)	Available Practical Deformation				Stress field matching	Suitable components
				Axial	Transverse	Shear	Rotation		
Knitted	Yes	3	-	>50%	>50%	>26%	N/A	No	Lightly loaded and very complex
Discontinuous aligned prepreg	No	3	Axial shear transverse	25% or more if very careful	50% or more if very careful	20% or more if very careful	Only when plied	Yes	Complex shapes and embossing. Max loads \approx 20% less than continuous prepreg. This can be improved with hybrid prepreg
Continuous prepreg	No	2	Shear transverse	Zero	30% or more if very careful	17% or more if careful	Only when plied	Yes	Highly stressed. Fairly simple or small components
Cloth	Yes	1	Rotation	Zero	Zero	N/A	30% from $\pm 45^\circ$ with 50% width reduction	No	Fairly complex shapes. Biaxial loading. UTS \approx 20% down on continuous prepreg cross-ply

TABLE 1

fibre direction necessary to protect the structure from off-axis loading. Any or all of these materials could be used locally in components which comprise large flat areas with some complex contours. For extremely complex mouldings a deformable material can be used to provide a structural backbone with moulding compounds keyed in to encompass the greatest intricacies. In cases like this where the usual materials would be castings, weight savings can be achieved - the greatest coming from the use of aligned discontinuous prepreg to control orientation.

MOULDING TECHNIQUES

There are two aspects of this to be considered, firstly how best to produce the required shape, and then the optimum moulding technique.

(1) Hand layup

Because deformations of cloth are reversible, this material should be almost foolproof in hand layup.

For discontinuous prepreg, hand layup requires some skill in the operation, but the danger of damage in the fibre direction is not too great since this is the hardest direction, and when shaping by hand deformation will naturally occur in the softest directions. The process of hand layup may sometimes be simplified by the use of a generic preform. That is to say the prepreg is laid up onto a shape which is similar to, but less complex than, the final object to be moulded with little or no deformation. This more robust, full thickness layup can then be safely and quickly deformed to the final shape, with constraint available from off axis plies to support any axial deformation.

(2) Mechanical methods

These fall into two groups, those that are imposed by the closure of a mould, with curing taking place immediately thereafter, and those used to produce a shape to be moulded as a separate operation.

The former technique has been used to draw hemispheres from cloth and punch out small objects from discontinuous aligned prepreg. The problem with this method is of course that there is no way of assessing how well the material has taken the shape before it is cured, so care must be taken to ensure that the reinforcement deforms as predicted. It will usually be necessary to prevent the reinforcement used from buckling out of its plane as it is drawn into the mould otherwise poor mould-filling and weak composites will be produced. With discontinuous aligned prepreg special care will have to be taken if embossing is required, as shear is a softer deformation mode than axial stretching. For both continuous and discontinuous prepreg the local stiffness of the material to deformation can be adjusted by altering the temperature, to give added control over the deformation process.

The second process is an extension of the use of backing sheets to support the deformation of unidirectional prepreg.

It involves the use of backing sheets as before, but with vacuum or air pressure to drive the backing sheet and prepreg into a cavity of the correct shape. Once more constraint should be used to prohibit buckling, and this can be such as to permit deformation in shear or, for discontinuous prepreg, to ensure that embossing occurs. If a rubber backing sheet is used then it must be sufficiently thick to control the deformation, since if the loads required to deform the prepreg are greater than for the rubber then separation and damage can still occur in the prepreg.

INFLUENCE OF THE MOULDING PROCESS

(a) Compression moulding

This technique gives the highest volume loading of fibre (up to 60% with aligned discontinuous fibre) and it is relatively cheap. If a large number of mouldings are required then this would be the preferred moulding technique to minimise the unit cost of component. For the compression moulding of components produced from deformable materials some special precautions are necessary. When an unfamiliar mould design is under consideration it may not be possible to predict the exact cured thickness of composite at each point in the mould. This is due to the changes in thickness that occur during deformation. For instance a hemisphere drawn from one piece of cloth varies in thickness by a factor of two around its perimeter. In a hard-faced mould this could lead to non-hydrostatic pressure and fibre-flow, both of which would be unwelcome. The problem can be overcome by covering one face of the mould with silicone rubber to ensure local accommodation to the moulding thickness and thus that hydrostatic pressure is achieved. The silicone rubber can also inhibit resin flow and hence permit fairly simple moulding cycles to be used.

An objection to this device is that the composite surface next to the rubber will not have a high surface finish. Where this is a problem then a moulding made with the silicone rubber can be used as a template for the manufacture of a matched metal mould.

(b) Autoclave moulding

This technique is simpler to set up than compression moulding because only one mould is required and this can be of a cheaper material than those used normally in matched-metal moulding. On the other hand moulding and layup times will be greater and thus labour costs will be higher using this form of moulding. Therefore autoclave moulding will probably be used for short production runs, large mouldings, and for shapes that are too complex for simple compression moulding. Normal autoclave techniques may be used with deformable materials, with few exceptions. If very complex mouldings are being made, the normal bleed/release products are inadequate as the release films are often non-deformable and might wrinkle on the surface of the moulding, as the bulk factor of the prepreg is taken up. It has been found that tight-fitting, thin silicone rubber bags make excellent release agents. They may either be used unperforated in zero bleed moulding, or regularly perforated by small holes to allow bleedout of resins. In the latter case either deformable felts or knitted glass cloth may be used to soak up the excess resin.

MOULD DESIGN

Because of the complexity of component available with deformable materials extra care must be taken when designing the mould, to ensure that the moulding can be safely and easily removed when cured. Provision must often be made for split moulds which can be jacked apart by screws or hydraulic jacks. These splits can easily be disguised by sitting them on edges or radii, but in any case very little flash along the split lines has been experienced in practice. Parallel sections or moulds must be carefully machined so as to avoid any adverse tapers which would make demoulding difficult.

CONCLUSION

As we have seen it is possible to construct a theoretical order of deformabilities in reinforcements. This order is overridden by the practical considerations that bring continuous prepreg down from its theoretical second place behind discontinuous prepreg, but still leave it some useful characteristics. Cloth emerges as a very simple to use and effective reinforcement. It will not however in general provide chosen orientations when draped on a double curvature, but a knowledge of its deformation behaviour may enable compromises to be made between the component shape and final fibre orientations. This knowledge also widens the

range of shapes attainable; by prestretching the cloth. To minimise the weight of components, control must be exercised over orientation which can only be done for complex shapes or where embossing is required by the partial or wholesale use of discontinuous aligned prepreg. This material also has other advantages. One form is available using high modulus brittle fibres that cannot easily be woven, and other intimately-mixed hybrid compositions can be selected to reduce cost and/or impart very useful properties.

It is natural to ask at this stage which material will be the one to concentrate resources on? The best answer is perhaps the frustrating one, that none of them should be overlooked. All of these deformable materials have a part to play in fabrication and it would be wrong to ignore one or more of them. This would lead to unnecessary restrictions on the components that are fabricable, or at the least add to the expense of and detract from the optimum performance/least weight criteria for the component.

Fig. 11 shows a component that has been made taking all these factors into account. It consists of a cylinder with a flange at one end which is twice the diameter of the cylinder. This was made from a generic preform consisting of a cylinder of cloth prestretched to $\pm 25^\circ$ to the cylinder axis interleaved with discontinuous aligned prepreg with the fibre direction along the cylinder axis. The final shape was made by simply opening up one end of this preform, the cloth was sufficiently extensible due to its prestretching and the prepreg was capable of being stretched 100% transversely due to constraint from the cloth. Thus the whole fabrication was quick and easy, the final orientations of the cloth were approximately correct and the discontinuous prepreg provided the third fibre direction needed to protect the biaxial array from off axis loading.

It can be seen from this that the study of the deformation modes of reinforcements is not merely an academic exercise, but can lead directly to simpler fabrication and more efficient structures. The reinforcements already available are capable of large amounts of deformation, so the ability to make complex parts simply, now depends more on the imagination and interpretation of fabricators, than on the development of better materials.

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